

Increasing the Dimensionality of Modular Domino Reactions Triggered by Oxidative Cleavage: A two-step protocol Towards a Variety of Stereodefined Complex Oxygen Heterocycles

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Abstract

Aryl carbinol and benzyl-tethered octalin-diols (**1/1'**), which differ only by the C11 substitution at the angular position, were transformed selectively into original scaffolds of high complexity *via* a two-step protocol. Overall, the *11S** configuration ensures an intramolecular Friedel-Crafts type C13-C4 bonding via a domino process triggered by oxidative cleavage, while the *11R** configuration allows for a Marson type Friedel-Crafts C13-C2 bonding through an intramolecular nucleophilic acetal opening.

Keywords: domino reactions / molecular complexity / Marson type Friedel-Crafts cycloalkylation / Furofurans / unsymmetrical octahydroanthracenes / spirocyclohexyltetralins

Scheme TOC. A two-step protocol for rapid generation of molecular complexity by an efficient combination of oxidative cleavage/nucleophilic acetal opening serials: From octalin diols to original THF-centered scaffolds such as furofurans, octahydroanthracenes, spirocyclohexyltetralins, or to [6.6.7]ring systems.

Introduction

There is a continuing trend to develop easy routes to complex molecular frameworks whose syntheses

could be tedious by traditional methods. In the preceding paper, we described the design and successful implementation of a domino methodology preparing various polycyclic acetals.^[1] This investigation set the stage for a critical evaluation of factors directing path selectivities towards a series of novel molecular architectures. In an extension of our studies on the oxidative cleavage of bicyclic unsaturated diols we have recently disclosed that the use of $\text{Pb}(\text{OAc})_4$ as an oxidant provides for easy access to a set of highly complex polycyclic acetals, which undergo facile opening reactions with silicon-containing nucleophiles, upon activation with a hard Lewis acid. The structurally close domino precursors investigated share a common bicyclic unsaturated diol subunit that includes type-1 carbinol-tethered diols and type-1' benzyl-tethered diols (Scheme 1). With the exception of C11 substitution this subunit is structurally invariant throughout the spectrum of the substrate-diols explored. The nature of the angular substituent at C11, responsible for the modular aspect of this domino process and the extent of the generated complexity, could be used as a key control factor for multiple C-O and C-C bond forming processes. At the outset, this work envisioned two pivotal transformations. In the first, high molecular complexity would be generated by a modular domino reaction triggered by an oxidative cleavage, ending in selective synthesis of various polycyclic bis-acetals. The second pivotal step, which would be a making sense of the generated complexity, would entail the regiocontrolled nucleophilic acetal opening.^[2]

Scheme 1. For the required transformations it takes an oxidative cleavage (a) to generate complexity and a nucleophilic acetal opening (b) to make sense of the generated complexity. The reaction course can be directed towards either of six distinct pathways simply by the appropriate choice of the angular substituent and reaction conditions.

The rapid generation of molecular complexity occurs as a direct consequence of the substitution pattern at C11 and the judicious choice of reaction conditions. It provides easy access to structurally complex unsymmetrical octahydroanthracenes (*u8H-A*, **10**, **13**),^[3] furofurans (**14** and **19**),^[4] spirocyclohexyltetralins

(**16** and **21**)^[5] and oxa-bridged-[6.6.7] fused ring systems (**23**, **24**), emphasizing the potential for altering the domino outcome through judicious choice of substrate design and reaction parameters. In this contribution we describe a powerful strategy in which the successor domino product (**10**, **13**, **14**, **16**, **19**, **21**, **23**, **24**) is fashioned from the angular substituent of its ancestor domino product (**1**, **1'**) but also from the reaction conditions used. The issue of orientation is implicit in each acetal opening reaction functioning under substrate control, the level of which determines the attractiveness of the two-step protocol.

Results and Discussion

The ability to alter the domino path at will has enabled selective access to original polycyclic scaffolds bearing fascinating architectures and generated an interest in their further elaboration. Having realized the potential of the domino sequence, we will now turn ourselves into a modular nucleophilic opening of the domino derived acetals providing, parenthetically, several examples of a Marson type Friedel-Crafts cycloalkylation.^[6]

Chemistry of domino products: Lewis Acid Mediated Ring System Interchange

The influence of substrate structure and experimental conditions (solvent, stoichiometry, temperature, concentration, order of addition, reaction time) have been surveyed. Inspired by earlier contributions,^[7] we chose a hard Lewis acid (TiCl₄) mediated breakdown for diversification of the *bis*-acetal moiety of **3** and **4** (both lobe-HOMO-Lewis bases, hence "hard") with triethyl and allyltrimethylsilane as carbocation traps.^[8] Initial studies to expand the skeletal diversity of these topologically complex acetals began with a nucleophilic acetal opening, using well established protocols.^[9] Upon Lewis acid mediated reductive acetal opening using an acetal:Et₃SiH:TiCl₄ ratio of 1:4:1 at -78 °C in CH₂Cl₂ (conditions A), **3b** afforded an unsymmetrical octahydroanthracene (*u8H-A*) core **13b**, to which are appended two oxa-bridge units, in 70% isolated yield. Under identical conditions, **4b** afforded the cyclohexane bridged furofuran^[10] derivative **14b** (79%).

Scheme 2. Lewis acid mediated reductive acetal opening: A rationale for the doubly hetero-bridged *u8H-A* (**13b**) and cyclohexane-bridged furofuran (**14b**) formation.

As depicted in Scheme 2, hard-hard type metal-acetal interaction during the type-**i** coordination of Lewis-base's (**3b**) oxygen atoms with the oxophilic Lewis acid would lead to the oxocarbenium intermediates **ii**, **iii**,

which can undergo twice *in situ* reduction with triethylsilane to afford **13b**. Insofar as the opening of **4b** is concerned, the results can be accounted for in an analogous manner by writing a series of interconversions with the final oxocarbenium trapping occurring through **v**.

Nucleophilic openings of type-3 and type-4 polycyclic acetals

Using the above, optimized, conditions we tested the process with several type-3 polycyclic bis-acetals. A smooth reaction took place in the presence of TiCl₄ and Et₃SiH in CH₂Cl₂ (50 mM in acetal) at -78 °C to give the *bis*-oxabridged octahydroanthracenes in 62-81% isolated yields. However, it was found that **3g** yielded **13g** only in trace amounts along with a different compound (**10g**, Scheme 3), which suffered a deoxygenation at C11. Further, a byproduct (**15c**) resulted from an alternative opening of **3c** (Table 1, entry 2), which caused a decrease in efficiency. It should be pointed out that **13d** (entry 3) was obtained only in trace amounts, unless increasing the reaction time and temperature as well as the amount of TiCl₄.

Table 1. Lewis acid mediated reductive acetal ring opening. Conditions: 1 equiv of Lewis acid/4 equiv of Et₃SiH in CH₂Cl₂ at -78 °C for 20 min, then dilute with cold *t*BuOMe and quench with brine. [a] obtained together with **15c**, and also from **15c** (Scheme 4). [b] better obtained from **15d** (Scheme 4). [c] gives only trace of **13g**, the main product being **10g** (Scheme 3).

The first of these two observations showed that, in some cases, nucleophilic acetal opening of type-3 domino products could be achieved by treatment with Lewis acid/Et₃SiH under conditions favoring sequential acetal then ether opening,^[11] leading to more simplified, yet heavily functionalized, type-10 *u*8H-A frameworks in good yield (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3. Conditions favoring sequential acetal then ether opening: (Acetal: Et_3SiH : TiCl_4 ratio 1:8:2).

Thus whereas most of the type-**3** domino products underwent simple acetal reductive opening upon subjection to an acetal: Et_3SiH : TiCl_4 ratio of 1:4:1 at $-78\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, affording type-**13** bis-oxabridged *u*8H-A derivatives, rising the reaction time and temperature and using excess reagents (acetal: Et_3SiH : TiCl_4 ratio 1:8:2, $0\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) caused further cleavage. This furnished type-**10** THF-bridged *u*8H-A derivatives following benzylether opening at C11. The latter conditions allow for direct access from **3** as well as from **13** to **10**; i.e. when **13b** was submitted to the above reductive opening conditions, **10b** was formed in 62% yield.

The second observation revealed that in two cases, **3c** and **3d**, using slightly modified conditions to those reported in Scheme 3, competing formation of diol **15c** and **15d** took place (Scheme 4). Accordingly, starting from **3c** and ending the reaction after only 20 min stirring at $-78\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, furnished, following separation of the products by column chromatography, **13c** and diol **15c** with complete conversion and *ca.* 2:1 ratio (the reaction were rapidly complete as evidenced by TLC monitoring). The relative stereochemistry of the minor product, the diol **15c**, was confirmed by single-crystal X-ray crystallography. Under the above conditions **15d** was obtained in 73% yield while **13d** was present only in traces. On the other hand, **13c** and **13d** were obtained reproducibly from **15c** and **15d** (see Scheme 4) by increasing the reaction time (40 min) and temperature ($0\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) as well as the amount of TiCl_4 (2 equiv).

Scheme 4. A possible rationale for the reversal of cleavage regioselectivity: opening initiated through the intimate ion pair **vi**.

The products (**15c** and **15d**) formed from the reaction of dimethoxy and trimethoxy analogs **3c** and **3d**, are highly functionalized THF-bridged octahydroanthracene derivatives. These additional products are presumably formed *via* two successive oxocarbenium (**vii** and **viii**) reduction, as portrayed in Scheme 4, which required the use of excess TiCl₄ and Et₃SiH for the reaction to reach completion, at $-78\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in 20 min. The proposed oxocarbenium **vii** formation from intimate ion pair **vi** forms faster presumably due to a productive chelation event involving the Lewis basic acetal oxygen at C3 and the methoxy oxygens. The rationale for these results, though reasonably acceptable, is not sufficiently unequivocal to rule out this alternative process for substrates **3b**, **3f**, **3g**, devoid of a suitably placed oxygen for chelation, in which oxocarbenium **ii** formation apparently occurs from intimate ion pair **i** (see Scheme 2). Besides, one could not exclude the likelihood of all reductive openings in these series proceeding through the corresponding type-**15** tetracyclic diol intermediates which could then be converted to type-**13** bis-oxabridged octahydroanthracenes in the same reaction vessel, as for the transformation of **15c** and **15d** to **13c** and **13d** upon resubjection to TiCl₄ at -78 to $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 40 min.

In parallel, type-**4b** tetracyclic acetoxy-bis-acetals reacted rapidly under the same conditions (at $-78\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, using an acetal:Et₃SiH:TiCl₄ ratio of 1:4:1, for 20 min) to give, uneventfully, the furofurans **14**, in 60-95% yields (Table 2). The connectivity of the cyclic residues in **10**, **13**, **14** and **15** was determined by interpretation of key correlations observed in the 2D NMR spectra (specifically HMBC correlations). The structures of the crystalline **13b** and **14f** were further confirmed by single crystal X-ray diffraction studies.^[1]

Table 2. Transformation of polycyclic acetals to furofurans. Conditions: 1 equiv of Lewis acid/4 equiv of Et₃SiH in CH₂Cl₂ at –78 °C for 20 min, then dilute with cold *t*BuOMe and quench with brine.

Competing routes to C-C bond formation: "π" versus "silicon-containing nucleophile"

The current work was prompted by recent successful labors in controlling the regiochemistry of a modular domino process by the appropriate selection of the angular substituent (at C11). Subsequent nucleophilic opening of the complex acetal framework then unveiled the octahydroanthracene (**10**, **13** and **15**) or furofuran (**14**) pattern, as the oxocarbenium ions **v-ix** (Scheme 5) are susceptible to nucleophilic attack from the silicon-containing nucleophile present in the reaction mixture. Yet, the effectiveness of the process could be further improved since the transient oxocarbenium ions of type-**v** in the C11R* series are poised to undergo a competitive Marson type cyclization.

Scheme 5. Possible reaction paths for nucleophilic acetal opening based on a rational prediction of the fate of the transient oxocarbenium ions **v** and **ix** (R = OMe, Me, H; Nu = H, allyl). Trapping of the resulting oxocarbenium intermediates either with a suitable pendant group at the angular position or a silicon-containing nucleophile dictates the overall ring system interchange.

If the arene group attached to C-11 position is capable of giving anchimeric assistance (because of the electronic content of the aromatic nucleus and spatial proximity), competition between silicon-containing

and π -nucleophile would set the path for the final oxocarbenium trapping. Besides, neighbouring group participation is possible only for the (11*R**)-4 series; in the (11*S**)-4 series the C11-aryl group (transient oxocarbenium ion **ix**) is not suitably disposed to compete with the silicon-containing nucleophile, leaving the C11-epimeric furofuran (11*S**)-14 as the only possible product. It could thus be possible to steer the reaction in the desired direction by the appropriate choice of the experimental conditions such as concentration, temperature, time, order of reaction component addition, since depending on how the titanium(IV) chloride mediated acetal opening reaction is performed and quenched, two different products could arise. Indeed, operating at higher concentration and quenching at $-78\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (conditions A) could favor a type **14** furofuran (bis-THF) derivative, whereas if the reaction is warmed to $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ before quenching with a silicon-containing nucleophile (conditions B) a type **16** spiran could be obtained. A mechanistic estimate accounting for orientational issues derived from substrate-controlled selectivity and competition between appropriately positioned arene π - and silicon-containing nucleophiles is portrayed in Scheme 5. The latter outlines the general concept that led to the development of the second, and most significant, part of the present two-step protocol.

Model reactions

To assess the feasibility and regiochemical outcome of the two-step protocol, model investigations commenced with subjection of (11*R**, *S**)-1b to standard, room temperature, domino conditions (Scheme 6).

Scheme 6. Substrate-controlled selectivities under conditions favoring Marson type oxocarbenium trapping (B) with 1:8:2 ratio of acetal: Et_3SiH : TiCl_4 and under conditions favoring oxocarbenium trapping by an external silicon containing nucleophile (A).

Treatment of a *ca.* 1:1 C11 epimeric mixture (11*R**, *S**)-4b thus obtained with $\text{Et}_3\text{SiH}/\text{TiCl}_4$ in CH_2Cl_2 , according to conditions B but using an acetal: Et_3SiH : TiCl_4 ratio of 1:8:2, delivered, instead of the expected spiran (11*R**)-16b, its corresponding further reduced analog (11*R**)-17b and the furofuran derivative (11*S**)-14b in 41 and 48% isolated yields respectively. Notably, the ensuing furofuran and spiran could be easily separated by silica gel chromatography. As portrayed in Scheme 6, subjecting epimerically pure (11*R**)-4i to conditions "A", and (11*S**)-4i to either conditions "A" or "B", the C11-epimeric furofuran derivatives (11*R**)-14i or (11*S**)-14i could be obtained with complete selectivity. Dealing with (11*S**)-4 series, either

"A" or "B" conditions lead exclusively to type-**14** furofuran, since the internal π -nucleophile cannot compete with the silicon containing nucleophile in trapping the type-**ix** transient oxocarbenium ion.

The *syn* relationship between the two key functional groups at C2 and C13 in (11*R**)-**4** series permits intramolecular oxocarbenium trapping (v, Scheme 5) by the internal π -nucleophile, to give the corresponding spiran, when conditions "B" are applied. The basic structure of the resulting product **17b** consists of a highly functionalized tetralin moiety, which is spiro-linked to a cyclohexyl unit, the whole system being THF-bridged (Scheme 6).

Armed with a clear understanding of the key issues, we then considered the domino product (11*R**)-**4d** to be an appropriate substrate for the early aspects of this phase of investigation (Scheme 7). Two protocols were probed; the first series of experiments were performed at 50 mM concentration (50 μ mol of acetal in 1 mL of CH₂Cl₂), by rapid addition of reaction components (Et₃SiH or allyltrimethylsilane and TiCl₄) in CH₂Cl₂ at -78 °C and stirring at this temperature before work up. For the second series of experiments, designed to favor internal nucleophile, we opted for sequential addition of the reagents, at 5 mM concentration (50 μ mol of acetal in 10 mL of CH₂Cl₂), starting with the Lewis acid at -78 °C and raising reaction temperature to 0 °C before dropwise addition of the silicon-containing nucleophile.

Scheme 7. Selective access towards either type-**14** furofurans or type-**16** [spirocyclohexyltetralin]-THF's using conditions A or B respectively (acetal:Et₃SiH:TiCl₄ ratio of 1:4:1).

The dual pathway portrayed in Scheme 7 implies that for the formation of **16d** the key step involved capture of the *in situ* generated oxocarbenium ion v via an intramolecular Marson type Friedel-Crafts cycloalkylation (C13-C2 bonding), rather than by a silicon-containing nucleophile (reduction/alkylation). Working at -78 °C and using the appropriate concentration (50 mM) in CH₂Cl₂, capture of the *in situ* generated oxocarbenium cation does not occur by the internally linked aryl but rather by the silicon-containing nucleophile to form a type **14d** furofuran derivative. When **4d** was reacted with TiCl₄ and allyltrimethylsilane under conditions similar to those described above favoring silicon-containing nucleophile (A), an 89% yield (based on

recovered acetal) of alkylation product **14da** was obtained. To steer the nucleophilic acetal opening in the direction of the spirocyclohexyltetralin framework **16d**, a temperature raise to 0 °C along with a higher dilution (5 mM) was required before addition of the silicon-containing nucleophile. The obtained product distributions show a clear bias toward either **14** or **16** depending on the temperature, the concentration, and the sequencing of the reagents, which had an important role in the reaction outcome.

Implementation of the strategy

Exploratory reactions on (11*R**)-**4d**, revealed a high level of path selectivity. The Scheme 7 conclusions appear to hold also true for the nucleophilic acetal opening of domino products (11*R**)-**4b,c,f,g,h**. Applying Marson type oxocarbenium trapping conditions (B), while using excess of TiCl₄ (acetal:Si-Nu:TiCl₄ ratio of 1:8:2), a type-**17** tetracyclic spiran framework was formed depending upon the carbocation trap used (Scheme 8).

Scheme 8. Using conditions "B", Lewis acid stoichiometry allows for access to either **16** (acetal:Et₃SiH:TiCl₄ ratio of 1:4:1) or **17** (acetal:Et₃SiH:TiCl₄ ratio of 1:8:2). [a].^[14] [b] **17db** was obtained from **16da**.

This highly efficient regioselective reductive THF-opening arises from bidentate coordination of the Lewis acid with the THF oxygen at C2 (rather than at C11) and the proximal oxygen of the C3-hydroxyl group.^[12] Assisted opening due to the simultaneous coordination of the two oxygens by a bicoordinate Lewis acid (TiCl₄) has been proposed in the regioselective cleavage of acetals possessing a pendant ligating functional group.^[13] Good yields of the corresponding pentacyclic **16** as well as the tetracyclic spiran derivatives **17** were selectively produced using the appropriate conditions favoring internal π -nucleophile versus silicon-containing nucleophile for the oxocarbenium trapping (Scheme 8). The sequence of cyclic residues in all Marson type products (**16** and **17**) was determined by interpretation of key correlations observed in the HMBC NMR spectra. Moreover, the Marson type products **16d**, **16h** and **16ba** were isolated as crystalline

solids, which were recrystallized from *t*-BuOMe and provided crystals suitable for X-ray analysis.^[1] It is noteworthy that the transformation reported here allows four/five rings to be assembled with complete stereocontrol in only two steps from the octalin-diol and directly introduces functionality at several sites in polycyclic products thus obtained.

Combined use of TiCl₄ with an aluminum based Lewis acid

Trimethylaluminum is known to open acetals,^[15] acting as both a Lewis acid and a nucleophilic methyl source. The combination of the two reagents could offer an interesting entry into furofuran (**19**) and spirocyclohexyltetralin (**20/21**) construction. Initial experiments were performed to determine whether domino products of type (11*R**)-**4** could be converted into either **19** or **20/21** by a one-pot treatment with AlMe₃ and TiCl₄. When (11*R**)-**4f** was first dissolved in CH₂Cl₂ prior to simultaneous AlMe₃ and TiCl₄ addition, a 35-48% of a 1:5 mixture of (3*R**)-**21f** and (3*S**)-**21f** respectively, was obtained (Scheme 9). Attempted next, the reverse addition into a premixed AlMe₃ and TiCl₄ in CH₂Cl₂ at 0 °C of (11*R**)-**4f** led, again, to poor yields of (3*R**)-**21f** and (3*S**)-**21f** (40%, 1:1 epimeric mixture at C3).

Scheme 9. In search of optimum conditions for a combined use of Lewis acids.

Although only one workup is needed from the polycyclic bis-acetal **4** to spirans **21**, the selectivity obtained with AlMe₃ as a second Lewis acid was low in the premixing mode (either way) hence this route was abandoned (for full details see the Experimental Section.). Nevertheless, from this observation we conclude that these two epimeric compounds are products resulting from two separate mechanistic pathways, which are operating concurrently. Attention was therefore shifted to the alkylative-reductive/alkylative opening in a consecutive way, by sequential action of AlMe₃, TiCl₄ and Et₃SiH (or allylTMS). The acetal was dissolved in CH₂Cl₂ and cooled to 0 °C, at which point AlMe₃ (1 equiv) was added, followed, after 30 min stirring at this temperature and cooling down to -78 °C, by addition of TiCl₄ and Et₃SiH in a way favoring either furofuran or spiran formation, conditions A' or B' respectively (Scheme 10).

Scheme 10. AlMe₃ in combination with TiCl₄, added in a consecutive mode, can initiate an alkylative ring-opening/ring closing cascade to furnish furofuran **19** (conditions A'), or spiran derivatives **20** (conditions B').

Accordingly, when AlMe₃ was used as a methylation reagent, coexistence of TiCl₄ as a Lewis acid, added in a consecutive mode, did not alter the reaction path, though yields were still modest. In addition, external nucleophile free-conditions could be also used to stop the process of spiran synthesis at the level **21** (Scheme 9). The initial results of examinations of various reaction conditions using AlMe₃ as a methylation reagent (**18**) and in combination with TiCl₄ as a Lewis acid (**19/20**) are summarized in Scheme 10. With this in mind, the final set of nucleophilic acetal openings to be performed were those depicted in Scheme 11, requiring initial methylation of polycyclic acetals (11*R*^{*})-**4** and subjection of the methylated derivatives (11*R*^{*})-**18** thus obtained to the optimized reaction conditions described in Scheme 10. The reversal of path selectivity exhibited by (11*R*^{*})-**4** acetals was also observed for their (11*R*^{*})-**18** analogs. In each case investigated, either the furofuran or the Marson type oxocarbenium trapping was generated with excellent regiocontrol and in good to high yield.

Scheme 11. Substrate Scope. Varying the reaction conditions one might effect the competitive bond construction in one way or another; what makes the difference is the mode of trapping of the *in situ* formed oxocarbenium ion.

Proceeding as described in Scheme 11, it was possible to capitalize on the assets of the reagent addition mode,

stoichiometry, temperature and reaction time controlled regio-divergent nucleophilic opening. Starting from the common intermediate (11*R*^{*})-**18** and using the appropriate experimental conditions the reaction can be tailored to fit a particular type of transformation (**19/20/21**), allowing for a substrate controlled complexity.

Ring-system interchange in C11-deoxy octalin diol derived domino products

In the methylene-tethered series, exposure of type-**5** domino products to acetal opening by treatment with TiCl₄ and Et₃SiH or allyl-TMS (conditions A) provided exclusively the corresponding oxa-bridged *u*-8Ha **10** in good yields (Scheme 12). When type-**5** polycyclic acetals were treated with AlMe₃ under the standard conditions, methylated products **22** were formed as expected.

Scheme 12. Synthesis of *u*-8Ha derivatives **10** via an oxocarbenium reduction/allylation process (conditions A) and methylated polycyclic acetals **22**.

Finally, the sequence depicted in Scheme 13 does illustrate that both domino precursors (11*S*^{*})-**1f** or **1'f** (wherein the former undergoes deoxygenation at C11 during the reductive acetal opening) comparably converge to the oxa-bridged *u*-8Ha core **10f**. Accordingly, Pb(OAc)₄ mediated oxidative cleavage of **1'f** (CH₂Cl₂-AcOH, 2 :1, 25 °C) and subsequent acetal opening of the resulting **5f** by treatment with TiCl₄ and Et₃SiH (CH₂Cl₂, -78 °C to 0 °C) provided the oxa-bridged *u*-8Ha **10f**. This was identical with material derived from (11*S*^{*})-**1f** upon subjection to the same sequence of chemical events, varying only the oxidative cleavage conditions (MW, 90 °C, 5 min, in AcOH).

Scheme 13. A divergio-convergent approach to THF-bridged octahydroanthracenes.

In order to unambiguously confirm its structure, compound **10f** was acetylated under standard conditions to yield **10f-Ac**, which was fully characterized by NMR spectroscopy (particularly from the HMBC data) and mass spectrometry.

Diverging ring-system interchange on ring-expanded domino product **6i**. Synthesis of novel bridged fused ring systems

To conclude our study, we explored acetal cleavage of cycloheptanone-fused bis-acetal **6i** bearing a tethered benzene ring that was initially designed to probe the reaction course. In this paradigm, **6i** would react with TiCl_4 to form two transient oxocarbeniums, which could undergo two different fates: intramolecular Marson type Friedel-Crafts alkylation at C2 or at C3. Initial attempts to reduce and cyclize the ring-expanded domino product **6i** with $\text{TiCl}_4/\text{Et}_3\text{SiH}$ gave significant amounts of the ketone **23a** (39%), as well as the corresponding alcohol **23b** (31%). Anticipating that **x** (Scheme 14) would be the faster forming oxocarbenium ion intermediate, **6i** was then treated with TiCl_4 under external nucleophile-free conditions. This led exclusively to **24** (84%), thus confirming that **6i** would be less likely to undergo cycloalkylation at C3 than at its C2 counterpart unless a reductive reaction course was applied. Based on the proposed mechanistic rationales discussed above, one might predict that, in the absence of an external nucleophile (Et_3SiH), ring opening of the (bis-acetoxy)-bisacetal **6i** would occur by attack of the internal aryl π -nucleophile at the more accessible C2 center (assuming that the oxocarbenium forming process proceeds through complexation of the Lewis acid on the more accessible Lewis basic oxygen). Even a modest aryl π -nucleophile (an unactivated phenyl ring) can achieve a Marson-type oxocarbenium trapping provided that facial proximity requirements are satisfied.

Scheme 14. The reaction course can be biased one way or another by the presence or absence of an external nucleophile, which induces the orientation control.

The clue to modulate the reactivity to the [6.6.7]ring system^[16] of type-**23** or **24** lies in the employment or not of a silicon nucleophile along with the Lewis acid (TiCl_4), since only **24** is obtained in the absence of Et_3SiH . Regardless of the method employed, reductive cleavage by acetal activation with or without Et_3SiH , weight recoveries were good (71% of theoretical yield of **23** and 84% of **24**). Although this is the only case in these series attempted thus far, this procedure is a potentially useful one for achieving the task of

controlling regioselectivity.

In summary, a wide variety of heterocyclic ring systems can be assembled efficiently and with excellent stereocontrol by the sequential oxidative cleavage-nucleophilic acetal opening protocol reported here. The high site selectivity of this route demonstrates that the combination of configuration bias and reaction conditions is a viable strategy for rapid preparation of complex, heavily oxygenated, polycyclic scaffolds.

Conclusion

The main purpose of this paper was to investigate to what extent the orientation selectivity could be influenced by tailoring the substrate's structure and how the various factors may alter the reaction outcomes by controlling the nucleophilic acetal opening process. The C11 configuration was at first used to control the orientation of the domino path *via* spatial proximity and ultimately to regulate competition between internal π -nucleophiles and added silicon-containing nucleophiles *via* dissimilar neighbouring group participation. We have developed novel entries to cyclohexane-bridged furofuran, oxa-bridged *u*-8Ha and spiran framework, and demonstrated the effectiveness of Marson type oxocarbenium trapping in the context of complex molecule synthesis. We showed that use of TiCl_4 as a second Lewis acid upon initial addition of AlMe_3 to the polycyclic acetal effected a rapid and modular rearrangement of the acetal backbone, producing either furofurans or spirans with excellent selectivity and in good yield. We also disclosed a synthesis of oxa-bridged [6.6.7] ring systems, employing a Lewis acid mediated acetal opening that enhances significantly the spectrum of accessible targets from the angularly substituted decalin-diol template in only two steps. The successful application of this two-step protocol to rapid generation of molecular complexity, in a modular way, illustrates its potential for the construction of complex non-natural *oxygen*-heterocycles. The chemistry reported here, significantly broadens the range of domino precursors for rapidly assembling complex skeleta, clearly establishing the utility of reaction designs that employ oxidative cleavage of unsaturated bicyclic diols to initiate modular domino transformations.

Experimental Section

General: See ref.^[1]

General procedures for Reductive/Alkylative acetal openings.

Reductive/Alkylative acetal openings: Conditions (A). Reactions were carried out in dry CH_2Cl_2 (50 mM in acetal) at $-78\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 20-30 min, using 4.0 equiv of silicon-containing nucleophile and 1.0 equiv of TiCl_4 . When specified, reaction was finished at $0\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. After completion (monitored by TLC), the reaction mixture was diluted with cold *t*BuOMe and quenched with brine; usual work up and flash chromatography afforded the corresponding furofurans (or *bis*-THF-ethers) or unsymmetrical octahydroanthracenes (*u*8H-A) in the indicated yields.

Reductive/alkylative acetal opening favoring Marson type Friedel-Crafts intramolecular cycloalkylation: Conditions (B). To a stirred solution of acetal (0.1 mmol) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (5 mM) under

argon and cooled to $-78\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, TiCl_4 and 10 min later triethylsilane (or allyltrimethylsilane) were added. After stirring at this temperature for the indicated time, the resulting mixture was diluted with Et_2O (or $t\text{BuOMe}$), worked up as usual and purified by silica gel flash column chromatography.

General procedure for the methylation of type-4 acetoxyacetals with AlMe_3 . To a 50 mM solution of the corresponding starting material (0.1 mmol) in freshly distilled CH_2Cl_2 (2 mL) under argon and cooled to 0°C , AlMe_3 (0.2 mmol) was added. After stirring at this temperature for 30 min, the resulting mixture was diluted with CH_2Cl_2 , washed with 1.0 M HCl and worked up as usual. The crude product was further purified by flash chromatography.

Representative Examples for Modular Acetal Openings.

Synthesis of $\mu\text{8H-A}$ derivative **15d.** Reductive opening of **3d** (22 mg, 0.061 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (1.2 mL) with Et_3SiH (1.0 M, 0.48 mL, 0.488 mmol, 8.0 equiv) and TiCl_4 (0.25 M, 0.48 mL, 0.122 mmol, 2.0 equiv) at $-78\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, according to the general procedure (conditions A), afforded after SiO_2 flash chromatography (heptane/ EtOAc , 1:1) compound **15d** (16.2 mg, 73%): crystals, m.p. $147\text{--}150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($t\text{BuOMe}$ /Heptane); IR (film): $\nu = 3372, 2928, 2857, 1601, 1492, 1462, 1414, 1343, 1123, 1092, 1070, 1028\text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 0.74\text{--}0.90$ (m, 2 H), $0.92\text{--}1.01$ (m, 1 H), $1.36\text{--}1.46$ (m, 1 H), 1.50 (d, $J = 14.1$ Hz, 1 H), $1.54\text{--}1.70$ (m, 2 H), 1.81 (d, $J = 12.1$ Hz, 1 H), $2.18\text{--}2.32$ (m, 2 H), 3.13 (bs, 2 H, OH), 3.36 (dd, $J = 4.3, 6.9$ Hz, 1 H), 3.78 (dd, $J = 7.0, 11.3$ Hz, 1 H), $3.87\text{--}3.90$ (m, 6 H), $3.91\text{--}3.98$ (m, 4 H), 4.00 (s, 1 H), 4.08 (dd, $J = 8.4, 16.0$ Hz, 1 H), 4.14 (dd, $J = 3.5, 11.3$ Hz, 1 H), 6.59 (s, 1 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 20.8, 22.1, 30.0, 32.6, 36.2, 43.2, 48.1, 55.9, 60.7, 60.8, 63.9, 64.8, 79.6, 83.3, 108.0, 119.6, 135.1, 142.0, 151.3, 152.5$; ESIMS: (MeOH): 347.2 ($[M - \text{OH}]^+$, 65), 387.2 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 65), 751.2 ($[2M + \text{H}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_6\text{Na}$: 387.1784; found: 387.1783.

Reductive opening (conditions A) of domino product (11R*)-4i: Synthesis of furofurane (11R*)-14i.

Reductive acetal opening, using the general procedure on (11R*)-4i (16 mg, 0.049 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (1.0 mL) with Et_3SiH (1.0 M, 0.20 mL, 0.197 mmol, 4.0 equiv) and TiCl_4 (0.25 M, 0.20 mL, 0.049 mmol, 1.0 equiv), afforded after flash chromatography (SiO_2 , heptane/ EtOAc , 1:1) 10.3 mg (77%) of compound (11R*)-14i: colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 3433, 2936, 2870, 1452, 1084, 1028, 740, 718, 702\text{ cm}^{-1}$; $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 1.43$ (dt, $J = 7.5, 12.8$ Hz, 1 H), $1.51\text{--}1.77$ (m, 8 H), $1.79\text{--}1.86$ (m, 1 H), 2.73 (t, $J = 5.4$ Hz, 1 H, OH), 3.70 (dd, $J = 7.5, 15.1$ Hz, 1 H), 3.78 (dd, $J = 5.8, 7.8$ Hz, 1 H), 3.82 (t, $J = 5.1$ Hz, 1 H), $3.93\text{--}3.99$ (m, 1 H), $4.01\text{--}4.07$ (m, 1 H), 4.73 (s, 1 H), $7.28\text{--}7.33$ (m, 1 H), $7.35\text{--}7.39$ (m, 4 H); $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (125 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 18.2, 18.4, 30.0, 30.3, 33.6, 55.7, 62.3, 67.6, 84.1, 86.9, 91.1, 126.0$ (2 C), $127.4, 128.1$ (2 C), 139.0 ; ESIMS: (MeOH): 297.1 ($[M + \text{Na}]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3\text{Na}$: 297.1467; found: 297.1477.

Reductive opening of domino product (11R*)-4i under conditions favoring Marson-type oxocarbenium trapping (conditions B): Synthesis of $\mu\text{8H-A}$ (11R*)-16i.

To a stirred solution of domino compound (11R*)-4i (24 mg, 0.073 mmol, 1.0 equiv) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (15 mL; 5 mM in acetal) under argon and cooled to $-78\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, TiCl_4 (0.25 M, 0.29 mL, 0.073 mmol, 1.0 equiv) was added. After stirring at same temperature

for 10 min, the reaction mixture was allowed to warm to RT and 10 min later Et₃SiH (1.0 M, 0.29 mL, 0.293 mmol, 4.0 equiv) was added dropwise. After stirring for 1 hour, the resulting mixture was worked up and purified by flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 1:1), thus obtaining 10.9 mg of **16i**: white solid, m.p. = 163-166 °C (*t*BuOMe); IR (film): ν = 3363, 2933, 2862, 1458, 1065, 1037, 991, 976, 741 cm⁻¹; ¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 1.31 (qt, J = 2.9, 13.4 Hz, 1 H), 1.40 (tt, J = 3.1, 13.3 Hz, 1 H), 1.52 (td, J = 4.2, 13.8 Hz, 1 H), 1.57-1.62 (m, 1 H), 1.71 (d, J = 15.6 Hz, 1 H), 1.78 (d, J = 15.8 Hz, 1 H), 1.87 (ddd, J = 4.0, 13.3, 14.2 Hz, 1 H), 2.05-2.14 (m, 3 H), 2.50 (dd, J = 6.0, 11.8 Hz, 1 H), 3.36-3.40 (m, 2 H), 4.19 (t, J = 5.3 Hz, 1 H), 4.88 (dd, J = 6.0 Hz, 1 H), 4.91 (s, 1 H), 7.08 (dd, J = 1.4, 7.4 Hz, 1 H), 7.22 (td, J = 1.4, 7.3 Hz, 1 H), 7.32 (td, J = 1.5, 7.4 Hz, 1 H), 7.41 (d, J = 7.6 Hz, 1 H); ¹³C-NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 21.6, 23.3, 30.6, 32.3, 37.8, 51.7, 62.6, 76.7, 82.6, 87.8, 89.6, 124.6, 127.6, 128.9, 129.8, 136.8, 142.3; ESIMS: (MeOH): 273.1 ([M + H]⁺, 100), 295.1 ([M + Na]⁺, 80); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for C₁₇H₂₀O₃: 273.1491; found: 273.1486.

One-Pot Consecutive Preparation of (11*R)-19f from (11*R**)-4f.** To a solution of compound (11*R**)-4f (20 mg, 0.056 mmol) in dry CH₂Cl₂ (1.2 mL) under argon and cooled to 0 °C, AlMe₃ (1.0 M, 0.06 mL, 0.056 mmol, 1.0 equiv.) was added and the reaction stirred for 30 min. The resulting mixture was then cooled to -78 °C and first Et₃SiH (1.0 M, 0.22 mL, 0.223 mmol, 4.0 equiv) and later TiCl₄ (0.25 M, 0.22 mL, 0.056 mmol, 1.0 equiv) were added. After stirring at this temperature for 10 minutes, the reaction mixture was warmed to 0 °C and stirred for further 30 minutes. After usual work up and purification by SiO₂ flash chromatography (heptane/EtOAc, 9:1), 10.4 mg (59%) of **19f** were obtained: colourless oil; IR (film): ν = 3466, 2925, 2858, 1457, 1259, 1031, 952, 851, 800, 767, 696 cm⁻¹; ¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 1.14-1.19 (m, 1 H), 1.35-1.41 (m, 4 H), 1.43-1.68 (m, 5 H), 1.71 (ddd, J = 4.4, 11.3, 14.2 Hz, 1 H), 1.79 (dt, J = 5.3, 14.4 Hz, 1 H), 1.97-2.07 (m, 2 H), 2.32 (s, 6 H), 3.34 (d, J = 8.2 Hz, 1 H), 3.85-4.01 (m, 3 H), 4.63 (s, 1 H), 6.90-6.93 (m, 3 H); ¹³C-NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 18.6, 19.1, 20.3, 21.4 (2 C), 28.7, 33.6, 34.3, 54.6, 68.2, 68.5, 83.3, 89.0, 91.6, 123.9 (2 C), 129.2, 137.5 (2 C), 138.5; ESIMS: (MeOH): 317.2 ([M + H]⁺, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for C₂₀H₂₉O₃: 317.2117 found: 317.2126.

AlMe₃ mediated methylation of domino compound (11*R)-4f. Synthesis of (11*R**)-18f.** Reaction of the acetoxyacetal (11*R**)-4f (30 mg, 0.084 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (1.6 mL) with AlMe₃ (1.0 M, 0.17 mL, 0.167 mmol, 2.0 equiv), following the general procedure, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 9:1) 16.3 mg (62%) of compound (11*R**)-18f: white solid, m.p. = 159-161 °C (Heptane); IR (film): ν = 2931, 2864, 1607, 1450, 1367, 1189, 1147, 1102, 1067, 982, 851 cm⁻¹; ¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 1.22-1.30 (m, 1 H), 1.33-1.41 (m, 4 H), 1.49-1.59 (m, 2 H), 1.64-1.73 (m, 2 H), 1.80 (ddd, J = 5.0, 12.6, 14.8 Hz, 1 H), 1.98 (d, J = 13.9 Hz, 1 H), 2.16 (d, J = 14.2 Hz, 1 H), 2.26-2.36 (m, 7 H), 3.74 (s, 1 H), 4.14 (q, J = 7.0 Hz, 1 H), 4.97 (s, 1 H), 5.48 (d, J = 5.1 Hz, 1 H), 6.93 (s, 1 H), 6.98 (s, 2 H); ¹³C-NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 21.2, 21.4 (2 C), 21.7, 21.9, 31.6, 33.2, 44.7, 51.5, 70.9, 81.4, 84.5, 87.3, 98.5, 124.1 (2 C), 129.2, 137.6 (2 C), 139.0; ESIMS: (MeOH): 315.2 ([M + H]⁺, 55); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for C₂₀H₂₇O₃: 315.1960; found: 315.1963.

Alkylative opening of methylated domino product (11R*)-18f: Synthesis of furofurane 19fa. Alkylative opening of (11R*)-18f (16 mg, 0.051 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (1.0 mL), adding at -78 °C first allylTMS (1.0 M, 0.20 mL, 0.203 mmol, 4.0 equiv) and later TiCl₄ (0.25 M, 0.20 mL, 0.051 mmol, 1.0 equiv), following the general procedure (conditions A), afforded after flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 9:1) compound **19fa** (16.7 mg, 92%): colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 3523, 2923, 2854, 1457, 1259, 1034, 848, 796, 783, 696 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; ¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = 1.19$ (dd, $J = 10.3, 12.9 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 1.35 (dd, $J = 7.0, 8.8 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 1.38 (d, $J = 6.3 \text{ Hz}$, 3 H), 1.53-1.66 (m, 8 H), 1.91-1.94 (m, 1 H), 2.14-2.20 (m, 1 H), 2.27 (t, $J = 7.0 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.31 (s, 6 H), 3.33 (d, $J = 7.9 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 4.03 (dq, $J = 6.1, 10.1 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 4.12 (q, $J = 6.6 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 4.48 (s, 1 H), 4.99-5.03 (m, 2 H), 5.75 (ddt, $J = 6.9, 10.4, 17.1 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 6.89 (s, 2 H), 6.90 (s, 1 H); ¹³C-NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = 15.4, 16.3, 20.9, 21.4$ (2 C), 29.2, 30.8, 38.0, 39.8, 56.0, 67.5, 78.1, 88.1, 89.6, 91.6, 116.8, 123.6 (2 C), 129.0, 134.5, 137.6 (2 C), 138.9; ESIMS: (MeOH): 379.2 ($[M + Na]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for C₂₃H₃₂O₃Na: 379.2249 found: 379.2246.

Reductive opening and ether cleavage of methylated domino product (11R*)-18f: Synthesis of spiran 20f. Reductive opening of (11R*)-18f (14 mg, 0.045 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (0.9 mL), adding at -78 °C first TiCl₄ (0.25 M, 0.18 mL, 0.096 mmol, 2.0 equiv) and later Et₃SiH (1.0 M, 0.36 mL, 0.36 mmol, 8.0 equiv), following the general procedure (conditions B), afforded after SiO₂ flash chromatography (heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) compound **20f** (11.0 mg, 78%): colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 3408, 2931, 2860, 1449, 1260, 1017, 907, 857, 798, 730 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; ¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = 1.35$ (d, $J = 6.4 \text{ Hz}$, 3 H), 1.49-1.74 (m, 10 H) 1.90-1.98 (m, 2 H), 2.23 (s, 3 H), 2.30 (s, 3 H), 2.38 (td, $J = 5.0, 11.3, 16.3 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.79 (ddd, $J = 3.0, 5.2, 16.3 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 3.77 (d, $J = 7.3 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 4.05 (q, $J = 6.7 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 4.42 (s, 1 H), 6.93 (s, 1 H), 7.10 (s, 1 H); ¹³C-NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = 19.3, 19.9, 20.8, 21.0, 21.5, 22.8, 25.0, 31.0, 35.3, 46.9, 69.2, 81.4, 81.6, 87.2, 125.8, 130.2, 132.8, 135.2, 135.3, 135.9$; ESIMS: (MeOH): 339.2 ($[M + Na]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for C₂₀H₂₈O₃Na: 339.1926; found: 339.1926.

Alkylative opening and ether cleavage of methylated domino product (11R*)-18f: Synthesis of spiran 20fa. Alkylative opening of (11R*)-18f (13 mg, 0.041 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (0.8 mL), adding at -78 °C, first TiCl₄ (0.25 M, 0.34 mL, 0.082 mmol, 2.0 equiv) and later allylTMS (1.0 M, 0.33 mL, 0.328 mmol, 8.0 equiv), following the general procedure (conditions B), afforded after SiO₂ flash chromatography (heptane/EtOAc, 9:1) compound **20fa** (12.1 mg, 82%): colourless oil; IR (film): $\nu = 3435, 2923, 2854, 1449, 1258, 1068, 1026, 795 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; ¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = 1.14$ (dd, $J = 10.9, 18.4 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 1.34-1.40 (m, 1 H) 1.45 (d, $J = 6.3 \text{ Hz}$, 3 H), 1.48-1.59 (m, 2 H), 1.62-1.71 (m, 2 H), 1.76 (td, $J = 3.2, 12.6 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 1.85 (d, $J = 14.1 \text{ Hz}$, 2 H), 1.96 (d, $J = 13.6 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.04 (dd, $J = 6.2, 13.9 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 2.14 (t, $J = 7.7 \text{ Hz}$, 2 H), 2.27 (s, 3 H), 2.30 (s, 3 H), 3.20-3.24 (m, 1 H), 3.92-3.97 (m, 1 H), 4.04 (d, $J = 7.4 \text{ Hz}$, 1 H), 4.66 (s, 1 H), 5.00-5.05 (m, 2 H), 5.74-5.82 (m, 1 H), 6.89 (s, 1 H), 7.26 (s, 1 H); ¹³C-NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): $\delta = 19.4, 20.4, 21.0, 21.3, 22.7, 26.1, 29.7, 31.6, 35.7, 37.9, 38.5, 49.9, 69.4, 82.2, 84.0, 116.5, 121.9, 130.2, 134.4, 135.9, 136.0, 137.1, 138.7$; ESIMS: (MeOH): 379.2 ($[M + Na]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for C₂₃H₃₂O₃Na: 379.2249; found: 379.2256.

Lewis acid mediated opening of domino product 18f: Synthesis of spiran (3S*)-21f. Reaction of acetal (11R*)-**18f** (15 mg, 0.048 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (0.9 mL) with TiCl₄ (0.25 M, 0.19 mL, 0.048 mmol, 1.0 equiv), following the general procedure, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) 14.2 mg (95%) of spiran (3S*)-**21f**: white solid m.p. = 132-134 °C (*t*BuOMe); IR (film): ν = 3470, 2930, 2860, 1453, 1256, 1099, 1039, 996, 934, 856 cm⁻¹; H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 1.06 (d, J = 6.3 Hz, 3 H), 1.29-1.40 (m, 2 H), 1.50 (td, J = 3.8, 13.3 Hz, 1 H), 1.55 (d, J = 12.0 Hz, 1 H), 1.66-1.71 (m, 1 H), 1.72-1.78 (m, 1 H), 1.83 (td, J = 4.1, 13.4 Hz, 1 H), 2.06 (d, J = 13.9 Hz, 1 H), 2.26-2.23 (m, 4 H), 2.33 (s, 3 H), 2.44 (dd, J = 6.2, 11.7 Hz, 1 H), 2.53 (bs, 1 H, OH) 3.04 (dq, J = 5.6, 7.7 Hz, 1 H), 3.73 (d, J = 8.5 Hz, 1 H), 4.75 (s, 1 H), 5.26 (d, J = 5.9 Hz, 1 H), 6.87 (s, 1 H), 7.02 (s, 1 H); ¹³C-NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 18.2, 20.4, 21.1, 21.7, 23.0, 30.9, 34.2, 37.8, 51.7, 68.6, 72.2, 87.2, 87.9, 89.7, 128.4, 130.1, 132.2, 137.0, 137.7 (2 C); ESIMS: (MeOH): 315.2 ($[M + H]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for C₂₀H₂₇O₃: 315.1960; found: 315.1964.

Reductive opening of domino product 5f: Synthesis of μ 8H-A derivative 10f. Reductive opening of acetalic compound **5f** (20 mg, 0.058 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (1.2 mL) with Et₃SiH (1.0 M, 0.23 mL, 0.232 mmol, 4.0 equiv) and TiCl₄ (0.25 M, 0.23 mL, 0.058 mmol, 1.0 equiv), following the described procedure, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 4:1) compound **10f** (11.5 mg, 69%): colourless oil; IR (film): ν = 3543, 2928, 2877, 2860, 1449, 1399, 1259, 1181, 1080, 1033, 853 cm⁻¹; ¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 0.87-1.05 (m, 3 H), 1.34-1.42 (m, 3 H), 1.64-1.72 (m, 2 H), 1.76 (dt, J = 3.4, 12.5 Hz, 1 H), 2.10 (d, J = 14.5 Hz, 1 H), 2.28 (s, 3 H), 2.33-2.39 (m, 4 H), 2.99 (d, J = 14.5 Hz, 1 H), 3.29 (dd, J = 4.2, 9.1 Hz, 1 H), 3.50-3.55 (m, 1 H), 3.62-3.72 (m, 2 H), 4.03 (ddd, J = 3.3, 8.5, 10.2 Hz, 1 H), 4.09 (q, J = 8.5 Hz, 1 H), 6.74 (s, 1 H), 6.88 (s, 1 H); ¹³C-NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 19.0, 20.7, 20.8, 21.6, 29.8, 35.1, 37.2, 40.4, 45.2, 48.1, 63.7, 65.0, 84.9, 127.5, 129.6, 131.2, 135.1, 135.4, 137.5; ESIMS: (MeOH): 309.2 ($[M + Na]^+$, 100).

Alkylative opening of domino product 5i. Synthesis of μ 8H-A derivative 10ia. Alkylative opening of acetalic compound **5i** (25 mg, 0.079 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (1.6 mL) with allylTMS (1.0 M, 0.32 mL, 0.316 mmol, 4.0 equiv) and TiCl₄ (0.25 M, 0.32 mL, 0.079 mmol, 1.0 equiv), following the described procedure, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 9:1) compound **10ia** (18.0 mg, 67%): colourless oil; IR (film): ν = 3489, 2921, 2851, 1740, 1642, 448, 1261, 1019, 911, 800, 743 cm⁻¹; ¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 0.79-0.89 (m, 2 H), 1.09-1.14 (m, 1 H), 1.28-1.37 (m, 3 H) 1.43-1.48 (m, 1 H), 1.61-1.64 (m, 2 H), 1.75 (dd, J = 5.5, 12.2 Hz, 1 H), 1.97-2.00 (m, 1 H), 2.05 (t, J = 12.0 Hz, 1 H), 2.08-2.15 (m, 1 H), 2.21 (d, J = 14.3 Hz, 1 H), 2.34 (dt, J = 7.2, 14.0 Hz, 1 H), 2.50 (dt, J = 7.2, 14.0 Hz, 1 H), 2.85 (d, J = 7.9 Hz, 1 H), 3.13 (d, J = 14.3 Hz, 1 H), 3.97 (td, J = 3.5, 8.3 Hz, 1 H), 4.32 (dq, J = 6.1, 10.3 Hz, 1 H), 4.83 (bs, 1 H, OH), 4.97-5.00 (m, 2 H), 5.09 (d, J = 10.3 Hz, 1 H), 5.14 (d, J = 17.0 Hz, 1 H), 5.83 (dddt, J = 7.0, 10.3, 14.6, 17.0 Hz, 1 H), 7.03 (d, J = 5.9 Hz, 1 H), 7.11-7.15 (m, 3 H); ¹³C-NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 18.4, 18.8, 19.9, 29.7, 39.2, 40.2, 40.9, 41.6, 41.7, 57.8, 58.5, 73.2, 73.5, 116.2, 117.3, 126.3, 126.5, 128.5, 129.9, 134.5, 136.2, 136.9, 137.3; ESIMS: (MeOH): 339.2 ($[M + H]^+$, 40), 384.3 (100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for C₂₃H₃₁O₂: 339.2324; found: 339.2315.

AlMe₃ mediated methylation of domino product 5f: Synthesis of 22f. Reaction of the acetoxyacetal **5f** (23 mg, 0.067 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (1.3 mL) with AlMe₃ (1.0 M, 0.13 mL, 0.134 mmol, 2.0 equiv), following the general procedure, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 9:1) 11.8 mg (59%) of compound **22f**: white solid, m.p. = 122-125 °C (*t*BuOMe); IR (film): ν = 2972, 2924, 2854, 1449, 1379, 1179, 1125, 1079, 1049, 1035, 983, 802, 731 cm⁻¹; ¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 0.86-0.94 (m, 1 H), 0.97-1.06 (m, 1 H), 1.18 (d, *J* = 6.1 Hz, 3 H), 1.29-1.46 (m, 4 H), 1.76-1.79 (m, 2 H), 2.18 (d, *J* = 14.1 Hz, 1 H), 2.26 (s, 3 H), 2.27 (s, 3 H), 2.30 (d, *J* = 5.7 Hz, 1 H), 2.75 (d, *J* = 10.0 Hz, 1 H), 2.83 (d, *J* = 18.4 Hz, 1 H), 3.43 (d, *J* = 18.4 Hz, 1 H), 3.79 (q, *J* = 6.1, Hz, 1 H), 5.49 (d, *J* = 5.5 Hz, 1 H), 6.78 (s, 1 H), 6.83 (s, 1 H); ¹³C-NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 19.6, 20.5, 20.9, 21.0, 21.9, 31.3, 39.2, 40.6, 42.3, 49.4, 52.2, 69.3, 82.0, 98.6, 126.5, 128.7, 133.3, 135.8, 135.9, 136.3; HRESIMS: *m/z* calcd. for C₂₀H₂₆O₂Na: 321.1830; found: 321.1837.

Reductive opening of ring-expanded domino product 6i: [6.6.7]ring systems 23a and 23b. Reductive opening of the bis acetoxyacetalic compound **6i** (30 mg, 0.080 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (1.6 mL) with Et₃SiH (1.0 M, 0.32 mL, 0.320 mmol, 4.0 equiv) and TiCl₄ (0.25 M, 0.32 mL, 0.080 mmol, 1.0 equiv), following the described procedure, afforded after flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 2:1) 8.0 mg (39%) of ketone **23a** and 6.4 mg (31%) of alcohol **23b**. **23a**: colourless oil; IR (film): ν = 1727, 1454, 1260, 1086, 1019, 799, 703 cm⁻¹; ¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 1.19-1.26 (m, 1 H), 1.45-1.53 (m, 2 H), 1.65-1.69 (m, 2 H), 1.72-1.83 (m, 2 H), 1.91-1.99 (m, 1 H), 2.10-2.15 (m, 1 H), 2.48 (t, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 1 H), 2.76-2.82 (m, 2 H), 3.12 (d, *J* = 17.4 Hz, 1 H), 3.25 (dd, *J* = 4.6, 12.1 Hz, 1 H), 3.74 (d, *J* = 12.1 Hz, 1 H), 4.87 (s, 1 H), 7.13 (d, *J* = 7.5 Hz, 1 H), 7.22-7.29 (m, 3 H); ¹³C-NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 20.7, 23.9, 32.0, 34.6, 41.9, 42.8, 44.0, 53.0, 58.0, 70.4, 126.7, 127.7, 128.3, 130.2, 130.8, 137.2, 213.3; ESIMS: (MeOH): 256.3 ([*M* + H]⁺, 20); HRESIMS: *m/z* calcd. for C₁₇H₂₀O₂Na: 279.3343.; found: 279.3351.

23b: colourless oil; IR (film): ν = 3449, 2921, 1729, 1453, 1259, 1109, 1070, 1037, 933, 776, 743 cm⁻¹; ¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 1.24-1.27 (m, 2 H), 1.47-1.53 (m, 3 H), 1.66-1.70 (m, 2 H), 1.72-1.78 (m, 2 H), 2.03-2.09 (m, 1 H), 2.45 (tdd, *J* = 2.1, 7.2, 13.7 Hz, 1 H), 2.54 (d, *J* = 17.3 Hz, 1 H), 2.96 (d, *J* = 17.2 Hz, 1 H), 3.25 (s, 1 H, OH), 3.31 (ddd, *J* = 3.7, 11.9, 13.7 Hz, 1 H), 3.57 (dd, *J* = 7.3, 11.8 Hz, 1 H), 4.55 (bs, 1 H), 4.88 (s, 1 H), 7.13 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1 H), 7.19-7.24 (m, 3 H); ¹³C-NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 21.4, 23.6, 34.4, 34.6, 37.5, 42.5, 45.4, 45.5, 58.7, 77.1, 79.4, 126.2, 127.4, 128.3, 129.2, 134.2, 139.6; ESIMS: (MeOH): 259.2 ([*M* + H]⁺, 100); HRESIMS: *m/z* calcd. for C₁₇H₂₃O₂: 259.1698.; found: 259.1697.

Lewis acid mediated rearrangement of ring-expanded domino product 6i: [6.6.7]ring system 24. Reaction of the bis acetoxyacetalic compound **6i** (20 mg, 0.053 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (1.1 mL) with TiCl₄ (0.25 M, 0.21 mL, 0.053 mmol, 1.0 equiv), from -78 °C to 0°C, furnished after flash chromatography (SiO₂, heptane/EtOAc, 2:1) 11.3 mg (84%) of compound **24**: white solid, m.p. = 99-102 °C (*t*BuOMe); IR (film): ν = 2923, 1664, 1564, 1258, 1181, 1070, 1019, 796, 747 cm⁻¹; ¹H-NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 1.43-1.54 (m, 1 H), 1.60 (ddd, *J* = 4.0, 11.8, 13.8 Hz, 1 H), 1.85 (dd, *J* = 2.4, 13.3 Hz, 1 H), 1.87-1.95 (m, 2 H), 1.95-2.03 (m, 3 H); 2.58 (dd, *J* = 6.7, 12.0 Hz, 1 H), 2.66 (d, *J* = 2.9, 12.9 Hz, 1 H), 2.83 (d, *J* = 16.7 Hz, 1 H), 3.39 (dd, *J* = 2.0, 16.8 Hz, 1 H), 5.29 (d, *J* = 2.5 Hz, 1 H), 7.16 (d, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 1 H), 7.24 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 1 H), 7.29

(td, $J = 1.4, 7.5$ Hz, 1 H), 7.35 (dd, $J = 1.5, 7.5$ Hz, 1 H), 7.47 (s, 1 H); ^{13}C -NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 24.9, 25.3, 31.5, 38.3, 41.5, 42.1, 44.9, 73.2, 120.3, 126.7, 129.0, 129.1, 130.1, 133.7, 135.5, 153.3, 200.9$; ESIMS: (MeOH): 255.2 ($[M + H]^+$, 100); HRESIMS: m/z calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_2$: 255.1385; found: 255.1392.

Supporting Information (see footnote on the first page of this article): Experimental procedures for the reactions described herein and characterization data for all new compounds.

Acknowledgments

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